

Temporal Stability of Protons and Neutrons: YasudaK Method of Validated Contributions from Temporal Multiplicative Factors of Quarks

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Abstract

This paper presents a detailed study on the temporal stability of protons, neutrons, and mesons, validated through precise experimental values. We propose a novel model based on the "Temporal Multiplicative Factors" of quark contributions, where each quark and gluon interaction adds to the stability of the particle. Updated results for isotopes such as Tritium, Carbon-14, and Helium-6 are provided, demonstrating the robustness of the model. Amplified fluxes and gluonic contributions during transitions, such as meson decays, are explained using a unified factorization framework, confirming their role in stability and decay dynamics. Furthermore, we emphasize the behavior of multiplicative factors as a precise mechanism for estimating temporal stability.

1 Introduction

The proton is one of the most stable particles in the universe, with a predicted lifetime of approximately 10^{34} years, while the neutron outside the nucleus decays in about 14.67 minutes. This dramatic difference in stability raises questions about the role of quark interactions, gluonic contributions, and amplified fluxes. In this work, we extend the "Temporal Multiplicative Factors" model to isotopes such as Tritium, Carbon-14, and Helium-6, providing updated calculations aligned with experimental data.

2 Methods

We model the proton, neutron, and meson lifetimes as a product of quark contributions:

$$\tau_{\text{system}} = (R_u \cdot P_u)^2 \cdot (R_d \cdot P_d) \cdot G, \quad (1)$$

where R_u , P_u , R_d , and P_d represent the rotational and propagative flows of the quarks, and G is the gluonic contribution. These contributions are di-

mensionless factors derived from experimental observations, scaled to result in the final lifetime expressed in years.

3 Results

3.1 Tritium Lifetime

The lifetime of Tritium is calculated as:

$$\tau_{\text{Tritium}} = 10^{34} \cdot 2.66 \times 10^{-24} \cdot (2.155 \times 10^{-5})^2 \approx 12.35 \text{ years.} \quad (2)$$

This result closely aligns with the experimental value of approximately 12.32 years.

3.2 Carbon-14 Lifetime

The Carbon-14 isotope's lifetime is derived as:

$$\tau_{\text{Carbon-14}} = 10^{30} \cdot 1.67 \times 10^5 \cdot 2.66 \times 10^{-24} \cdot (1.136 \times 10^{-4})^2 \approx 5732 \text{ years.} \quad (3)$$

This result is consistent with the experimental value of 5730 years.

3.3 Helium-6 Lifetime

For the Helium-6 isotope, the lifetime is calculated as:

$$\tau_{\text{Helium-6}} = 10^{10} \cdot (7.076) \cdot (7.78) \cdot (2.155 \times 10^{-10})^2 \approx 2.56 \times 10^{-8} \text{ years.} \quad (4)$$

This corresponds to approximately 0.807 seconds, matching experimental observations.

4 Discussion

The updated model's alignment with experimental values highlights the reliability of temporal multiplicative factors in predicting particle stability. Specifically:

- Tritium's lifetime reflects the precise interplay between proton, neutron, and pion contributions.
- Carbon-14 demonstrates the stabilizing effects of additional neutron interactions, enhanced by meson contributions.
- Helium-6 showcases the instability induced by peripheral neutrons relying on shared pion structures.

The model further emphasizes the importance of counter-rotational fluxes of Up quarks (u) and Down quarks (d), which govern the temporal regulation within nuclear systems.

Figure 1: Illustration of the temporal interactions between protons, neutrons, and mesons in Tritium, Carbon-14, and Helium-6, highlighting the rotational fluxes and gluonic contributions.

5 Conclusion

This study demonstrates that particle stability and decay can be precisely described through multiplicative factors of quark contributions. The updated results for Tritium, Carbon-14, and Helium-6 validate the model's predictive power, paving the way for its application to more complex systems.